

IMPROVING TRAFFIC SAFETY OF VEHICLES AT SECONDARY
CROSSROADS WITH LIMITED VISIBILITY OF HIGHWAYS

Urinov Dilmurod Ulmasboevich

*Andijan Machine-Building Institute, Assistant of the Department of
"Transportation Organization and Transport Logistics"*

ANNOTATION

In this article, the mechanism of crossing with a moving vehicle at a secondary intersection in the conditions of limited visibility of highways was considered, free zones were identified. Study and develop the movement of drivers at the intersection without changing the mode of movement of the road, the zone of prevention of road accidents when applying emergency braking and "dead zone".

Keywords: highway, traffic safety, unregulated intersections, limited visibility, dead zone.

INTRODUCTION

The purpose of this study was to assess the possibility of safe crossing of an unregulated unequal intersection by a secondary road, the conditions under which dangerous situations occur, and the possibility of preventing a car collision under limited visibility conditions.

LITERATURE ANALYSIS AND METHODOLOGY

A car moving along the secondary road should stop in front of the stop line, cross the sidewalk, and give way to cars on the main road and start moving. To assess the possibility of a safe passage, the driver of a vehicle traveling on the secondary road must see the vehicle moving on the main road at a greater distance. The presence of cars parked on the sidewalk of the main road, at a distance of 10m from the edge of the road crossing according to traffic rules, significantly limits visibility

SK is the distance the vehicle stopped at the stop line of the secondary road to the possible collision of the vehicle (to simplify the subsequent analysis, the width of the carriageway is assumed to be equal to the total width of the vehicle).

$$S_k = S_d + B_o + y \quad (2)$$

Here, SP is the parking distance of the car on the main road to the boundary of the middle road (SP minimum distance, according to traffic rules, 10 m);

SL is the distance from the left edge of the road to the left side of the secondary road, passing through it;

B is the distance from the left side of the vehicle to the driver's seat;

y - side-by-side clearance between the vehicle traveling on the main road and the vehicle;

A is the distance from the front of the car to the driver's seat;

Ba is the width of the car;

Bo is the distance from the right edge of the main road to the left side of the car on which it is parked;

Sd is the distance from the stop line on the secondary road to the boundary of the main road;

A car traveling on the secondary road will need time for the car traveling on the main road to pass before it reaches its lane. In this case, it is necessary to travel safely.

$$\frac{S_b - b}{v_1} \geq \frac{\sqrt{2 * (S_k + B_a + L_a) * j_p}}{j_p} - \frac{\sqrt{2 * S_p * j_p}}{j_p}$$

It is also possible to prevent a vehicle collision if the driver of a car traveling on the secondary road begins to take measures to reduce the speed of the car immediately before the car stops when the car appears on his lane on the main road.

DISCUSSION

The path is from the beginning of the movement to the end. In this case, in its acceleration mode, the distance to the SP and the stopping path will be SP2, and should not exceed Sk.

$$T_{II} = t_1 + t_2 + t_3 * 0.5 \quad (3)$$

Here, the reaction time of the t1-driver; t2-brake drive delay time; growth time of t3-deceleration; acceleration of the vehicle during jr-acceleration, m / s2; Decrease of the vehicle during JT-braking, m / s2; t2-vehicle acceleration, then the speed at which it is possible to stop during emergency braking, the total distance not exceeding Sk.

RESULT

The stopping path is determined by the following formula:

$$S_0 = (t_1 + t_2 + t_3) * V_a + \frac{V_a^2}{2 * J_t} \quad (4)$$

If the vehicle is moving on the main road and applies braking when danger arises, its travel time will increase and its lane will be sufficient to be crossed by the vehicle

Figure 2. Order of view zones.

CONCLUSION

1. According to the existing rules, parking in the area of road intersections significantly limits the visibility of cars and determines the presence of dangerous places for the movement of vehicles, when to avoid a collision, drivers change the mode of transport (up to emergency) The need to take measures can also ensure that no action of drivers in the "dead" area will prevent accidents.
2. Improving road safety is only a systematic approach to traffic organization at the intersections of their actual account parameters.
3. The impact of visibility on the intersection possibilities of unequal roads requires in-depth research.
4. The proposed method of analysis can be used in the examination of the possibility of preventing accidents on unregulated sections of unequal roads.

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